

Figure 8 — Preisach plane and endogenous trend synchronisation

Preisach Plane — investor hysteron state
Blue=long, Gold=short | x=SL cascade, +=TP

Two INDEPENDENT Preisach-MHTAR series
Cascade dynamics can synchronise trends accidentally

